

Supporting the EU Mission "A Soil Deal for Europe" across national communities

To establish 100 Living Labs and Lighthouses

Funded by
the European Union

Supporting the EU's ambitious “Soil Deal for Europe” to restore soil health by 2050 through Innovation and Knowledge Beacons.

The main objective of NATI00NS is reaching out to and preparing regional and national stakeholders to apply for and implement soil health Living Labs and Lighthouses (LLs), facilitating the deployment of the EU Soil Mission across European regions during most of the first ‘induction and pilot’ phase (2021-2025).

European Commission

Between 60 and 70% of EU soils are estimated to be unhealthy. Soil is a fragile resource that needs careful management and preservation for future generations. One centimetre of soil can take hundreds of years to form, but can be lost in just a single rainstorm or industrial incident.

NATI00NS acts as a messenger of the Mission, raising awareness among national and regional stakeholders, providing access to quality-checked capacity building materials and information, spurring the discussions on the best LL setups to address regional soil needs, and fostering early matchmaking for cross-regional LL clusters.

Our offer

NATI00NS' main outcomes will consist of supporting the formulation and submission of high-quality applications through a combination of national and transnational events addressing key topics related to the EU Soil Mission. These will be accomplished between 2023 and 2024.

Stakeholder engagement

NATI00NS contributes to the EU Soil Mission goals and objectives by mobilising national groups of stakeholders, as potential applicants for regional soil health LLs Open Calls funded by the EU Mission Soil. Their main results will be reported back to provide policy recommendations.

NATIONAL EVENTS

- Soil health challenges and resilience strategies
- Events in 43 countries, including EU MS and AC

THEMATIC EVENTS

- Soil health
- Agri-food innovators
- Business care
- Industrial land stewardship
- Urban & forest environments

TRAINING MATERIALS

- Supporting applicants to draft competitive applications

CAPACITY BUILDING

- Online courses and sessions to tackle key questions

HELPDESK

- Digital platform providing support from experts

MATCHMAKING B2B EVENTS

- Matching cross-regional LL clusters

NATIOONS Pillars

Balance

The consortium is looking for maximum stakeholder outreach. On the one hand, all Horizon Europe MS and AC will be targeted, ensuring equal distribution of activities. On the other hand, relevant actors will be involved in each country, seeking a balanced engagement of stakeholders from different land uses.

Knowledge

NATIOONS is counting on top-quality partners to convey the information to potential LLs applicants, gathering multi-disciplinary expertise on soil sciences, stakeholder participatory processes, land management practices in different land uses, economics, nature-based solutions, as well as on the soil policy landscape, focussing on key initiatives such as EU Missions, Farm to Fork Strategy, Biodiversity Strategy, Soil Strategy, European Green Deal, SDGs, and more.

Adaptability

The Soil Mission is a living initiative. We will quickly adapt to eventual changes in priorities and objectives of the Mission. National engagement events and activities to support applicants are set for immediate implementation.

NATIOONS Partners

NATIOONS partners and Advisory Board members include different stakeholders: from multidisciplinary academic partners to EU umbrella organisations representing specific groups, like farmers, public authorities, Living Labs, industry and business, multi-actor organisations and NGOs.

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Join the community

We will publish contents and materials and host training sessions to support the submission of high-quality application forms for the EU Mission Soils Open Calls.

Check out
for updates